

Jul and Aug plantings, but increased for Sep plantings and reached 12 insects/sweep for Oct plantings. The population declined during the relatively cool months of Dec and Jan (Fig. 1).

Incidence of the bacilliform virus (RTBV) and the spherical virus (RTSV) increased with leafhopper populations. Regardless of month of planting, RTSV incidence was present (Fig. 1b). Infection with RTSV alone did not cause RTV symptoms. Dual infection with RTBV and RTSV was observed in Jun, Sep, and Oct plantings. Regardless of month of planting, TN1 was most infected, followed by IR36 and IR42 (Fig. 1c). IR50, IR58, and IR64 were seldom infected. □

Average density of the vector leafhoppers (a) and incidence of RTBV and RTSV (b) at 30 d after transplanting in 6 varieties transplanted monthly from Jun 1985 to Jan 1986; and incidence in each variety regardless of month of transplanting (c).

A scoring system for rice yellow mottle virus disease (RYMV)

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RYMV, an African specific disease of lowland rice varieties, has been studied for its etiology and to screen for resistance. But a standard evaluation system for this disease has not been reported.

The disease is systemic and variable under different growing conditions. Symptoms vary with age of host. Different varieties show different symptoms. Even after repeated inoculations, some immune varieties do not show any virus serologically, even

by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). Others with little or no symptoms give positive reactions with ELISA.

The scoring system we propose is compatible with the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. Scores are based on leaf color, mottling, plant height, flowering,

Table 2. Differential varieties for RYMV.

Score	Resistance grade	Varieties
0	HR	<i>Oryza glaberrima</i> accessions such as Tog 5612, Tog 5681
2	R	Moroberekan, LAC23
4	MR	OS6, ITA235
7	S	BG90-2, IR5
9	HS	ITA212

and sero-reaction determined by agar-gel diffusion and ELISA techniques. The serological techniques are for restricted use in critical laboratory tests. Most field scores can be based on visual symptoms.

In the score range, 0 represents immunity and 9 extreme susceptibility (death of infected plant) (Table 1).

The actual score range is typified by certain rice varieties which when inoculated display characteristic symptoms (Table 2). □

Table 1. Scoring system for RYMV.

Score	Resistance ^a	Leaf color	Stunting	Flowering	Sero-diagnosis ^b	
					ELISA	Agar-gel diffusion
0	HR	Green	Nil	Normal	-	-
1	R	Green	Nil	Normal	+	±
2	R	Green	Nil	Normal	++	+(weak)
3	R	Green with sparse dots/streaks	Negligible	Normal	+++	+
4	MR	Green with visible mottling	Slight	Normal	+++	++
5	MR	Light green, mottled	25%	Slight delay	Highly positive	
6	S	Pale green	50%	Delayed	Highly positive	
7	S	Pale yellow	75%	Delayed	Highly positive	
8	S	Yellow	>75%	No flowering	Highly positive	
9	HS	Yellow, orange	>75%	Death of plants	Highly positive	

^aHR = highly resistant, R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible, and HS = highly susceptible. ^b± = doubtful, - = negative, + = low virus content, ++ = high virus content, +++ = very high virus content.

Crown sheath rot incidence in West Bengal

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Early symptoms of crown sheath rot were reddish brown lesions in patches on the outer leaf sheaths at the crown of the plants. Gradually, the lesions spread throughout the crown sheaths and became dark brown to black. At maturity, clusters of perithecia were produced in the lesions. In severely affected clumps, the culms rotted causing incomplete exertion and leaf drying (see figure).

Microscopic examination of the rotted crown sheaths showed the